

Study to Evaluate ECG Markers for Detection of Left Ventricular Systolic Dysfunction.Amit Kumar¹, Dhananjay Singh Shekhawat², Chandra Bhan Meena³¹Senior Resident, Department of Cardiology, S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur²Assistant Professor, Department of Cardiology, SMS Medical College, Jaipur³Senior Professor, Department of Cardiology, S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur

Received: 12-11-2023 / Revised: 18-12-2023 / Accepted: 22-01-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Early diagnosis of severe LV dysfunction with echocardiography improves outcome. But in developing country like India echocardiography and other advance imaging are not available in peripheral centre. We selected a combination of electrocardiogram (ECG) markers for screening of individuals with severely reduced LVEF.

Methods: A single centre cross-sectional observational study was conducted including 160 cases with LVEF <35% and 160 control with LVEF >35%. Subjects were evaluated for prevalence of conventional ECG markers and association of nine additional ECG markers with LV dysfunction.

Results: Conventional ECG abnormalities LBBB observed in 20% case and 5% control with significance ($p=0.001$), atrial fibrillation observed in 11.8% case and 9.3% control ($p=0.47$) with no significance. At least one major ECG abnormality was observed in 46(28.75%) of cases with LVEF $\leq 35\%$ and 22(13.75%) control with LVEF >35% ($p < 0.002$). Abnormal > 4 ECG parameter was observed in 15(9.37%) cases with LVEF $\leq 35\%$ and 4(2.5%) control with LVEF >35% ($p < 0.016$). The presence of any one of these abnormalities for predicting LVEF $\leq 35\%$ produced a sensitivity of 83%, specificity of 55%. Except delayed QRS transition and delayed intrinsicoid deflection rest other parameter were significantly associated with LVEF $\leq 35\%$ ($p < 0.05$)

Conclusions: An expanded panel of nine obtained ECG markers correlated strongly with severely reduced LVEF. This electrical surrogate score could facilitate screening of severely reduced LVEF, and warrants further evaluation.

Keywords: echocardiography, electrocardiography, left ventricular ejection fraction, left ventricular systolic dysfunction.

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Introduction

The heart is an electric generator and electromechanical pump. [1] Electric excitation initiates mechanical contraction, orchestrates excitation–contraction coupling, and coordinates myocardial pumping. Changes in the frequency, regularity, and order of cardiac electric excitation can cause electric heterogeneity, dyssynchrony, ventricular dysfunction, and ultimately clinical pump failure. [2–4] While inherited long QT syndrome (LQTS) has historically been considered a purely electrical disease, echocardiographic studies over the past two decades have demonstrated a crude but replicable relationship between a prolonged QT interval and abnormal mechanical function. [5] Observational data paired with animal studies suggest that electrical transmural dispersion of repolarization, manifest on the surface electrocardiogram (ECG), can be associated with mechanical dispersion of left ventricular relaxation

observed using comprehensive echocardiography. [6]. Several studies have shown a positive association between LV size (diameter, volumes, and length) and QRS duration. [7,8,9] Agreement between ECG-LVH and LV mass has been extensively studied. [10] ECG-LVH predicts cardiovascular outcomes independent of LV mass. [11,12,13] There are no specific ECG features unique to LV dysfunction, however the ECG is usually NOT normal.

The most common ECG abnormalities are those associated with atrial and ventricular hypertrophy — typically, left sided changes are seen but there may be signs of biatrial or biventricular hypertrophy. Interventricular conduction delays (eg. LBBB) occur due to cardiac dilatation. Diffuse myocardial fibrosis may lead to *reduced* voltage QRS complexes, particularly in the limb leads. There may be a discrepancy of QRS voltages with signs of

hypertrophy in V4-6 and relatively low voltages in the limb leads. Abnormal Q waves are most often seen in leads V1 to V4 and may mimic the appearance of a myocardial infarction ("pseudoinfarction" pattern). Left atrial enlargement -> may progress to atrial fibrillation, Biatrial enlargement, Left ventricular hypertrophy or biventricular enlargement, Left bundle branch block (LBBB can also occur), Poor R-wave progression with QS complexes in V1-4 ("pseudo-infarction" pattern), Frequent ventricular ectopics and ventricular bigeminy (seen with severe DCM), Ventricular dysrhythmias (VT / VF).

Heart failure (HF) with severely reduced left ventricular ejection fraction LVEF $\leq 35\%$ remains a major public health problem in the India, with an average 5-year mortality of 50% due to pump failure or sudden cardiac death [14]. Severely reduced LVEF is detected by cardiac imaging, mostly echocardiography, but due to practical and cost-effectiveness considerations, broad deployment of imaging tools for screening of asymptomatic patients in the community is not viable. Myocardial electrical remodeling is a consistent feature of the HF syndrome and manifests as abnormalities in the 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG), reported in a variety of patient populations. However, published studies of the association between electrical remodeling with left ventricular (LV) dysfunction are relatively small and have focused mainly on a limited number of individual ECG variables, largely atrial fibrillation, left bundle branch block (LBBB), and ventricular pacing.

Material and Methods

This study is a single centre cross-sectional observational study with study period of 18 months and was conducted in department of cardiology, SMS Medical college Jaipur (Rajasthan). Patients were selected randomly for sample size of 160 case. Aim of the study is to identify combination of electrocardiogram (ECG) markers for severely reduced LVEF.

Patients with LVEF $\leq 35\%$ identified from the echocardiography were included in the study. ECGs with evidence of acute ST-elevation MI and ventricular paced rhythms were excluded. Patient were evaluated for major ECG abnormalities (AF

and LBBB) and expanded panel of all nine of abnormal ECG markers associated with reduced ejection fraction.

The nine parameters of the expanded ECG panel are the following:

1. heart rate >85 bpm
2. P-wave duration >110 ms
3. PR interval >200 ms
4. QRS duration >110 ms
5. QTc interval (Bazett's correction ≥ 460 ms for men and ≥ 470 ms for women).
6. frontal QRS-T angle $>90^\circ$; (calculated as the absolute difference between the frontal QRS axis and T-wave axis with values $0^\circ-180^\circ$)
7. delayed QRS transition zone (R-wave amplitude less than S-wave amplitude in lead V4)
8. delayed intrinsicoid deflection (defined as R-peak time ≥ 50 ms in lead V5 or V6)
9. left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH; by Cornell voltage).

In addition 160 age and sex matched healthy control with normal ejection (EF $> 50\%$) fraction were looked for major and expanded panel of ECG marker.

Statistical analyses were performed with SPSS 2021 version. Chi-square tests were used for univariate associations, and automated stepwise logistic regression to test the multivariable-adjusted association of each ECG marker, with LVEF $\leq 35\%$ as the outcome and the nine individual ECG markers as predictors as the independent variables. Logistic regression models were calculated, one with ECG variables as continuous predictors if appropriate, and the second model with all ECG variables dichotomized. Continuous ECG variables will be dichotomized at clinically accepted cut-points: heart rate >85 bpm; QRS duration >110 ms; QTc interval ≥ 460 ms for men and ≥ 470 ms for women; QRS-T angle $>90^\circ$; PR interval >200 ms; and P-wave duration >110 ms.

Observation

We enrolled 160 patients with LVEF $<35\%$ and 160 healthy age and sex matched control in this cross-sectional observational study.

Table 1: Demographics and electrocardiogram parameters based on left ventricular ejection fraction.

Demographics	LVEF $\leq 35\%$ n= 160	LVEF $> 35\%$ n= 160	p -value
Age	44.2 \pm 13.8	44.8 \pm 12.9	0.65
Female sex n(%)	26(16.25%)	22(13.75%)	0.44
BMI	22.7 \pm 2.7	23 \pm 2.7	0.42
Conventional abnormal ECG finding.			
Left bundle branch block (LBBB) (n,%)	20%	5%	0.001
Atrial fibrillation(n,%)	11.87	9.3%	0.47

Table 2: Univariate analysis of expanded panel of electrocardiographic variables in subset without conventional ECG abnormalities .

variables	LVEF \leq 35% n= 160	LVEF \geq 35% n= 160	p- value
Heart rate >85 bpm	42.5%	24.37%	0.009
QRS >110 ms	35%	7.5%	0.001
Prolonged QTc \geq 460 ms men and \geq 470 ms women	46.25%	10%	0.001
QRS-T angle >90°	20%	7.5%	0.002
Delayed QRS transition	18.75%	11.8%	0.06
Delayed intrinsicoid deflection	10%	3.75%	0.19
Left ventricular hypertrophy (Cornell voltage)	21.87%	12.5%	0.04
PR >200 ms	10%	1.87%	0.05
P-wave >110 ms	35%	6.8%	0.001

Table 3: Multivariate logistic regression analysis of expanded panel of electrocardiographic variables.

variables	Odds ratio	95% confidence interval for odds ratio	p- value
Heart rate >85 bpm	1.996	1.108-3.594	0.021
QRS >110 ms	6.491	3.059-13.776	0.001
Prolonged QTc \geq 460 ms men and \geq 470 ms women	8.335	3.993-17.397	0.001
PR >200 ms	3.243	0.546-19.252	0.195
P-wave >110 ms	7.732	3.456-17.298	0.001
Delayed QRS transition	0.388	0.149-1.005	0.051
QRS-T angle >90°	2.549	0.987-6.581	0.053

Table 4: Comparison of abnormal >1 ECG parameter and >4 ECG parameter with ROC curve analysis.

	Case N=160	Control N=160	p-value	ROC curve area	Asymptotic 95% confidence interval (ROC curve)
Abnormal > 1 ECG parameter	46(28.75%)	22(13.75%)	0.002	0.758	0.704-0.811
Abnormal > 4 ECG parameter	15(9.37%)	4(2.5%)	0.016	0.534	0.471-0.598

Abnormal > 1 ECG parameter

Abnormal > 4 ECG parameter

Observation:

We enrolled 160 cases with LVEF < 35% and 160 age and sex matched control with LVEF >35% control in this single centered cross-sectional observational study. Anthropomorphic and clinical characteristics of the study group are presented in Table 1. No significant differences were noted in

age, sex and BMI between the case and control. Conventional ECG abnormalities LBBB observed in 20% case and 5% control with significance (p=0.001), atrial fibrillation observed in 11.8% case and 9.3% control (p=0.47) with no significance. So the presence of LBBB was significantly associated with LVEF \leq 35% while AF was not associated with lower ejection fractions . At least one major ECG

abnormality was observed in **46(28.75%)** of cases with LVEF $\leq 35\%$ and **22(13.75%)** control with LVEF $> 35\%$ ($p < 0.002$) (Table 4). The presence of any one of these abnormalities for predicting LVEF $\leq 35\%$ produced a sensitivity of 83%, specificity of 55%. In univariate comparisons of all nine of the expanded ECG parameters except delayed QRS transition and delayed intrinsicoid deflection rest other parameter were significantly associated with LVEF ≤ 35 ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2). In the multivariable model, heart rate, QTc interval, QRS duration, prolonged P wave and LVH remained independently associated with LVEF $\leq 35\%$, while prolonged PR, QRS-T angle delayed QRS transition zone and delayed intrinsicoid deflection interval were not significant (Table 3).

Based on the five statistically significant ECG markers, an unweighted expanded ECG panel sum was constructed ranging from ≥ 4 abnormal markers. Abnormal > 4 ECG parameter was observed in **15(9.37%)** of cases with LVEF $\leq 35\%$ and **4(2.5%)** control with LVEF $> 35\%$ ($p < 0.016$). There was no significant interaction by sex with the ECG panel sum ($p = 0.44$). The expanded ECG panel was significantly associated ($p < 0.001$) with decreasing LVEF in the validation population. Among patient with expanded panel of ECG parameter those with QTc prolongation had more LV dysfunction (OR-8.335 95% CI(3.993-17.397)) followed by p wave duration(OR-7.732 95% CI(3.456-17.298)) and QRS duration(OR-6.491 95% CI(3.059-13.776)).

Discussion

This study evaluated association of different sets of ECG marker apart from conventional ECG markers in identifying LV dysfunction. Among patients with major ECG abnormalities that are conventionally associated with LVEF, such as 11.87% atrial arrhythmias and 20% LBBB had LVEF $\leq 35\%$. In the remaining patients without conventional ECG abnormalities, five specific ECG parameters (heart rate, QTc interval, QRS duration, prolonged P wave and LVH) remained independently associated with LVEF $\leq 35\%$. Case with ≥ 4 abnormal ECG markers correlated strongly with LVEF $\leq 35\%$ and in individuals with one or no abnormal ECG markers, severely reduced LVEF was not a common finding. Published studies have reported a correlation between abnormal ECG diagnoses such as atrial fibrillation, LBBB, ventricular paced rhythms and reduced LVEF; and in clinical practice, these findings generally prompt clinicians to evaluate the LVEF. [15]

However, a large subgroup of patients will have reduced LVEF in the absence of these conventionally accepted ECG markers. There is need of improvement for identification of patients with severely reduced LVEF.

The association between several individual ECG markers and LVSD has been previously reported. For example, increased resting heart rate has been associated with reduced LVEF even in asymptomatic individuals in the general population. [16] Several studies among HF patients and other populations

have linked QRS prolongation with decreased LV systolic function. [17] However, early attempts to directly estimate LV function using measures of QRS morphology from the ECG had limited success. [18] The more-specific depolarization measures included in the expanded panel, that is, delayed intrinsicoid deflection and QRS transition zone, were individually associated with low LVEF [19,20]. Prolonged QTc-interval and wide QRS-T angle have been associated with LV dysfunction. [21,22]. There are very few study in which combination of all ECG parameter of LV dysfunction has been analyzed.

In this study, after excluding patients with major ECG abnormalities conventionally associated with LV dysfunction, 9.37% of patients had ≥ 4 abnormal ECG findings. This study, in accordance with previous reports (Nielsen et al.), suggests that a normal ECG virtually excludes severe LV dysfunction. [23]. All these findings imply that a markedly abnormal electrical profile, even in the absence of other conventionally used major ECG abnormalities, is strongly correlated

with LV systolic function. There are factors that can explain the relationship between increasing number of ECG abnormalities and decrease in LVEF. Pathologic LV remodeling in ischemic or non-ischemic cardiomyopathy has electrical components that are reflected as abnormalities in cardiac conduction and myocardial depolarization/repolarization markers.[17,21]. Structural and electrical remodeling contribute independently to risk of morbidity and mortality. [24] Manifestation of the HF syndrome is abnormal autonomic remodeling, reflected by increased resting heart rate. [25]

Conclusions

Apart from conventional ECG marker of LV dysfunction i.e atrial fibrillation and LBBB, an expanded panel of nine obtained ECG markers correlated strongly with severely reduced LVEF. This electrical surrogate score could facilitate screening of severely reduced LVEF, and warrants further evaluation.

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